

Pharmacological studies of new oxidants – *N*-Bromonicotinamide and *N*-chloronicotinamide

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Abstract : The compounds *N*-bromonicotinamide (NBN), *N*-chloronicotinamide (NCN) and nicotinamide (NA) have significant effect on locomotor activity when compared to the standard drug. The compounds NBN, NCN and NA did not show a significant enhancing effect on phenobarbital induced narcosis when compared to the standard drug.

Keywords : *N*-Bromonicotinamide (NBN), *N*-chloronicotinamide (NCN), nicotinamide (NA), locomotor activity, narcosis.

Introduction

Natural products are a rich source of organic substances which are used for the production of many drugs. These organic substances were isolated and subjected to detailed investigations for their structure and physiological activity of a compound is associated with a particular structural unit or a functional group known as pharmacophore group. It was observed that if the pharmacophore group is removed then the compound loses its activity. If the compound having a particular pharmacophore group is found to be toxic, then this group is somewhat modified by using simple reactions to yield a new compound which is physiologically more active or is less toxic or both. 1-(3-Indolylmethyl *N,N*-diethyl) hexahydronicotinamide was found to lower blood pressure, decrease the heart rate and block the pressure rise resulting from bilateral carotid occlusion at dose level of 2–16 mg/kg. The physiological activity of many substituted piperidines prompted the scientists to design simple methods for the synthesis of piperidine carboxamide derivatives. During the studies of correlating the structure and cardiovascular activity in the past several decades, various derivatives of piperidinecarboxamide compounds (hexahydro-nicotinamide and -isonicotinamide) had been reported by various workers. They found to possess spasmolytic and antihypertensive activities. In searching of new hypotensive agents, substituted hexahydronicotinamides were prepared

by Swaim¹. They caused a decrease in blood pressure after intravenous injections into dogs anaesthetized with α -chlorates while 1-(3-indolyl-methyl) carotid occlusion at dose level of 2–16 mg/kg. In past several decades indole derivatives have attracted the interest of scientists for their potential biological activities. Different acylated azaindole compounds have been reported for analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities. Several other indole derivatives have been prepared as cyclooxygenase inhibitors and were found useful as anti-inflammatory agents. One indole derivative designated as indomethacin has demonstrated a high degree of anti-inflammatory and analgesic activity. The azaindole derivatives were also found to possess blood pressure lowering activity and acting as effective coronary vasodilator, cardiovascular and potent hypotensive agent. Synthesis and investigation of azaindole derivatives² for different pharmacological and biological effects have been an important subject of research. Nicotinamide phosphoribosyltransferase (NAMPT), also known as visfatin, is the rate-limiting enzyme in the salvage pathway of NAD biosynthesis from nicotinamide. Pharmacological inhibition of nicotinamide phosphoribosyltransferase and enzymatic activity to identify a new inflammatory pathway linked to NAD was studied by Nathalie Busso³ and co-workers.

The art of synthetic chemistry has always been a significant tool to design pharmacoactive compounds, a wide

screening, development of active analog and random discovery is a valuable and widely employed method for drug discovery. A completely new era in medicine began in mid nineteenth century with the discovery of number of therapeutically active heterocyclic compounds. These heterocyclic compounds play increasingly expanded role in drug design.

The search for new drugs with reduced toxicity and lower side-effects is continuous. Nicotinamide represents a very good nucleus for preparation of some sedative/hypnotic and anti-convulsant agents, since such a heterocyclic system possesses the pharmacophore moiety⁴. Nicotinic acid is one of the heterocyclic compounds, which is simple derivative of pyridine. The amide form of nicotinic acid acts as a biochemical catalyst in various physiological processes⁵⁻⁷. It is available in its neutral form in liver, meat, fish, poultry, whole grains and legume. Large doses of nicotinic acid may have undesirable effects such as flushing of skin, GIT disturbances, nigrican acanthosis, increased risk of development of gallstones, hyperpigmentation and dryness of skin. Therefore, nicotinamide and its derivatives are preferred to nicotinic acid in therapeutics. A significant amount of work has therefore, been devoted to the synthesis of its analog with a view to modify the pharmacological applications. Considerable work has been carried out for the past several decades to study the central nervous system activity (CNS) of nicotinamide, hexahydroisnicotinamide and their derivatives⁸⁻¹³. It seemed likely that various hexahydroisnicotinamide derivatives would have CNS activity such as anticholinergic, antiserotonin activity, anxiolytic, antidepressant, local anaesthetic, antiarrhythmic and antipsychotic activities. In exploring the CNS active agents, such aryloxy alkyl derivatives of piperidine and analogs were found useful for the treatment of CNS diseases. Several novel derivatives of piperidine had been synthesized for their CNS potentials and proved to be effective in the treatment of psychiatric illness and other CNS disorders.

The cytotoxicity of nicotine, nicotinic acid, nicotinamide and hexahydroisnicotinamide had been studied by different workers. The antineoplastic activity of some of the nicotinamide derivatives have been reported by different scientists.

A novel series of nicotinamide and hexahydroisnicotinamide derivatives were synthesized by Saify and stud-

ied for different pharmacological activities. Considerable interest is focused to synthesise some new derivatives of hexahydroisnicotinamide and to evaluate these compounds in order to ascertain their therapeutic potentials with the goal of improving potency to a great extent but less toxic having fewer side effects.

Mechanisms of action :

Nicotinamide acts as an antioxidant by preventing NAD depletion during DNA repair by inhibiting poly (ADP-ribose) polymerase (PARP), which also modulates major histocompatibility complex (MHC) class II expression. Nicotinamide inhibits free radical formation and facilitates beta-cell regeneration *in vivo* and *in vitro*. Additional protection from macrophage toxins may be involved in prevention of type 1 diabetes. Specifically, niacinamide has been shown, via PARP inhibition, to protect pancreatic islet-cell lysis after exposure to oxygen free radicals and nitric oxide. Nicotinamide has also been found to stimulate GABA receptors, without binding to the receptor sites, thus creating a benzodiazepine-like effect.

Clinical indications :

Anti-inflammatory action affecting neutrophil chemotaxis has been reported for niacinamide. Nicotinamide has been used successfully to prevent or delay the onset of type 1 diabetes among high-risk individuals, defined by high islet-cell antibodies and family history of type 1 diabetes.

Nicotinamide and niacin have been used since 1940 or earlier to treat a number of psychiatric conditions. Hoffer is a strong advocate of the use of nicotinamide in the management of schizophrenia. A study by Mohler found nicotinamide to produce an anti-anxiety effect equivalent to a highly potent benzodiazepine. It has also been presumed that patients with sub-clinical pellagra, who have developed perceptual changes and neurasthenia, could be labeled as schizophrenic and would benefit from treatment with nicotinamide.

Joint dysfunction improved in arthritic patients using frequent high doses of nicotinamide. Nicotinamide has been used to treat several types of dermatological pathologies. In addition, nicotinamide has been used successfully in the treatment of other blistering skin diseases when used in conjunction with tetracycline. Nicotinamide

has also been shown to be effective in the treatment of cutaneous hyperpigmentation, which occurs in multiple conditions. Animal studies found simultaneous supplementation of nicotinamide with radioactive iodine treatment of hyperthyroid goiter increased effectiveness of radiation at lower doses due to nicotinamide's radiosensitization. Concomitant use of nicotinamide and antiepileptic drugs, specifically carbamazepine, diazepam, and sodium valproate, apparently potentiates the anticonvulsant action of these drugs. In addition, nicotinamide⁶ may decrease clearance of carbamazepine when used simultaneously.

Objective :

To study the effect of *N*-halosubstitution on nicotinamide side chain on the pharmacological activity in general, CNS activity, sedative or hypnotic activity and anticonvulsant activity in particular. It is also of interest to compare the pharmacological activity of nicotinamide and its chloro- and bromo- derivatives.

Central nervous system activity :

The drugs act on central nervous system of the human body which consist of brain and spinal cord, and controls and regularizes the special functions like circulation, digestion and respiration and it also modifies the psychic reactions such as feeling, attitude, thoughts and memory. The ability to think logically, to remember the past experiences, communication are unique qualities of man which can be attributed to the development of highly specialized central nervous system. The drugs which affect the central nervous system can either stimulate or depress the central nervous system.

Sedative and hypnotic activity :

Hypnotic is a drug that induces sleep. Sedative, on the other hand is a drug (dose of a drug) that calms or soothes without inducing sleep though it may cause sleepiness. Almost all hypnotics, when used in small doses throughout the day will produce sedative effect, and the same drugs when used in larger doses before retiring to bed will cause sleep. Therefore the only difference between the hypnotics and sedatives is one of the degree.

The study of amino acids becomes important because of their biological significance and selectivity towards the oxidant to yield different products. *N*-Bromonicotinamide (NBN) is ideal for the facile oxidation of or-

ganic substrates. This oxidant offers advantages like easy method of synthesis, low cost, low toxicity and mild nature with appreciable stability. *N*-Bromonicotinamide (NBN)¹⁵ has been used as effective oxidant for the oxidation of α -amino acids¹⁶⁻²⁰. It has been screened for antibacterial and antifungal activities²¹. *N*-Chloronicotinamide (NCN)²² has been used for the oxidation of α -amino acids^{23,24}, aromatic aldehydes²⁵ and alcohols²⁶. As *N*-bromonicotinamide (NBN) possesses antibacterial and antifungal activities, it is worthwhile to determine the pharmacological evaluation of the compound and compare with its chlorine analog *N*-chloronicotinamide (NCN) and nicotinamide (NA), the parent compound.

Results and discussion

The compounds *N*-bromonicotinamide (NBN), *N*-chloronicotinamide (NCN) and nicotinamide (NA) have significant effect on locomotor activity when compared to the standard drug. NBN, showed maximum inhibition of 10.43% while its chlorine analog and parent, namely, NCN and NA showed 14.81% and 18.37% respectively. The standard drug, chlorpromazine showed maximum inhibition of 52.60% (Table 1). The results of gross behavioral assessment indicated that the active compounds produced a depressant effect on the central nervous system.

Table 1. Pharmacological data of reference and test compounds

Treatment	Locomotor activity (scores) in 10 min		
	Before treatment	After treatment	Decrease in activity (%)
Control	142.68 ± 0.38	139.26 ± 0.17	2.39
Standard	152.26 ± 0.06	72.16 ± 0.42	52.60
NBN	152.59 ± 0.32	136.67 ± 0.38	10.43
NCN	150.28 ± 0.41	128.02 ± 0.52	14.81
NA	149.72 ± 0.26	122.21 ± 0.32	18.37
<i>P</i> < 0.001 PVs standard.		NBN (<i>N</i> -Bromonicotinamide)	
Control : Normal saline 5 ml/kg		NCN (<i>N</i> -Chloronicotinamide)	
Standard : Diazepam 3 mg/kg		NA (Nicotinamide)	
Values are expressed as ± SEM			

The animals were still responsive and did not exhibit any prominent muscle relaxation. This may be responsible for the modification of mesolimbic system²⁷.

All CNS depressants have some ability to relieve anxiety, at doses that produce noticeable sedation. Most anxiolytic and sedative-hypnotic drugs produce dose – dependent depressant of central nervous system functions.

As the test compounds *N*-bromonicotinamide (NBN), *N*-chloronicotinamide (NCN) and nicotinamide (NA) have significant effect on locomotor activity, naturally they will not have significant sedative or anxiolytic activity. From the results of the above study, it is found true.

N-Bromonicotinamide (NBN), *N*-chloronicotinamide (NCN) and nicotinamide (NA), did not show a significant enhancing effect on phenobarbital induced narcosis, when compared to the standard drug, namely, Larozepam. The compounds under study, NBN, NCN and NA shown 59.0, 44.2 and 71.5% activity respectively (Table 2).

Table 2. Pharmacological data of reference and test compounds

Treatment	Dose of compound (mg/kg)	Sleeping time (%)	Sleeping time with phenobarbital (%)
NBN	50	59.0	122.5
NCN	50	44.2 ^a	96.8
NA	50	71.5	117.4

^a*P* < 0.01, compared with standard drug.

Control : Normal saline 5 ml/kg	NBN (<i>N</i> -Bromonicotinamide)
Standard : Larozepam 0.5 mg/kg	NCN (<i>N</i> -Chloronicotinamide)
	NA (Nicotinamide)

The anticonvulsant effect of the test compounds, namely, *N*-bromonicotinamide (NBN), *N*-chloronicotinamide (NCN) and nicotinamide (NA) showed no antiepileptic activity, compared to that of phenobarbitone sodium. The substitution of nicotinamide hydrogen by chloro- or bromo- group makes no difference towards antiepileptic activity compared to that of parent, nicotinamide.

Experimental

Synthesis of NBN and NCN :

N-Chloronicotinamide (NCN) :

A slow stream of chlorine was passed into a solution of nicotinamide (NA) (15 g in 30 ml 3 *N* hydrochloric acid) at 32 °C for 30 min. The NCN formed as a white precipitate was filtered and the processes of passing chlorine into the filtrate and the filtering of the precipitate were repeated till no more precipitate was obtained. The precipitate was filtered, washed with ether and recrystallised from ethanol²³.

N-Bromonicotinamide (NBN) :

N-Bromonicotinamide was prepared by a modification of the method by which bromobenzamide and its

derivatives were prepared²⁸. 10 g of pure, finely pulverized nicotinamide was added to 150 ml of an ice-cold solution of sodium hypobromite, freshly prepared from 14.4 g (0.09 mole) of bromine and 9.0 g (0.23 mole) of sodium hydroxide. After shaking for 10 min, the mixture was filtered rapidly under suction into a cold solution of 9 ml of glacial acetic acid in 25 ml of water containing crushed ice. The bromamide which precipitated was filtered off and washed thoroughly with water. The product was recrystallised from ethanol (m.p. 210 °C). The yield was 70% of the theoretical quantity.

Nicotinamide (NA)

N-Bromonicotinamide (NBN)

Animal experimentation :

Pharmacological evaluation of the compounds was carried out in the Department of Pharmacology, Periyar College of Pharmaceutical Sciences for Girls, Trichy, Tamilnadu, India. The animals were maintained at a well ventilated, temperature controlled animal room for seven days prior to the experimental period and provided with food and water *ad libitum*. The animals were acclimatized to laboratory conditions before the test. Each animal was used only once. Animals, female mice (*Iffa credo*, France), 18–22 g, were used. The animals were allowed free access to food and water and were housed at room temperature (20–22 °C). All the test compounds were administered via intraperitoneal injection in distilled water with Tween-80 solution.

Central nervous system activity :

Actophotometer²⁹ was used to evaluate the locomotor activity. The Swiss albino mice (20–25 g) were divided into eight groups each consisting of six animals. The test compounds *N*-bromonicotinamide (NBN), *N*-chloronicotinamide (NCN) and nicotinamide (NA) were injected i.p. One group received standard chlorpromazine 3 mg/kg and one group received vehicle (normal saline 5 ml/kg i.p.). All the remaining six groups received between 8.5 to 12.3 mg/kg of test compounds NBN, NCN and NA i.p. The locomotor activity score of all the animals was noted by placing the animals in the square area of the

instrument for 10 min. Each mouse was retested for activity score after 30 min of the test drug administration. The difference in the activity before and after the administration of standard chlorpromazine and test compounds was noted. The percentage decrease or increase in motor activity (%) was calculated.

Sedative and hypnotic activity :

Barbituric narcosis³⁰ was used to evaluate the sedative and hypnotic activity. Barbiturates exhibit the same type of tolerance as the narcotics. Swiss albino mice (20–25 g) were divided into eight groups each consisting of six animals. The test compounds *N*-bromonicotinamide (NBN), *N*-chloronicotinamide (NCN) and nicotinamide (NA) were injected i.p. One group received standard Larozeepam 0.5 mg/kg and one group received vehicle (normal saline 5 ml/kg i.p). All the remaining six groups received between 8.5 to 12.3 mg/kg of compounds NBN, NCN and NA i.p 30 min before a hypnotic dose of Phenobarbital (35 mg/kg i.p). The parameter quantified was the sleeping time to abolition of the righting reflex when the mice was placed on their work.

Antiepileptic activity :

Electro shock method :

Electro shock method³¹ was followed to study the antiepileptic activity. Wistar rats of either sex (120–150 g) were used in this study. The positive control used was phenytoin (25 mg/kg i.p). The control group was fed with the normal saline 5 ml/kg i.p. All the remaining six groups received between 8.5 to 12.3 mg/kg of test compounds NBN, NCN and NA i.p. Supramaximal electroshock of 150 mA for 0.2 s by a technoconvulsimeter was given to the rats through corneal electrodes³².

Swiss albino male mice, weighing 20–25 g, were obtained from an animal facility. Mice were housed in stainless steel wire-floored cages without any stressful stimuli. Room temperature was kept at 23 ± 2 °C. Animals were fed standard laboratory chow and tap water *ad libitum*. Mice were randomly arranged in different groups, six in each. Test compounds, were suspended in Tween-80 (0.2%) (Sigma, USA) and were given i.p. in doses ranging from 50–100 mg kg⁻¹ body mass. Dosing volume was 0.2 ml per 20 g. Phenobarbitone sodium (Sigma) was dissolved in water in 2% concentration and used as a reference standard and it was given i.p. in doses of 3.25,

6.5 and 12.5 mg kg⁻¹. Pentylene tetrazole was dissolved in water in 2% concentration and was given i.p. in a dose of 100 mg kg⁻¹ one hour after the test compounds or phenobarbitone sodium³³. The animals were observed for convulsions. Animals that showed no convulsion within one hour after PTZ injection were considered to be protected.

Conclusion :

Compounds NBN, NCN and NA showed maximum inhibition of 10.43, 14.81 and 18.37% respectively. NBN has significant effect on locomotor activity compared to the standard drug. It produced a depressant effect on the central nervous system. The compounds NBN, NCN and NA did not show a significant enhancing effect on phenobarbital induced narcosis when compared to the standard drug.

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References

1. Shamim Akhtar, Z. S. Saify, M. Arif, Nousheen Mushtaq, Ahsana Dar and Ashfaq Ahmed, *Pak. J. Physiol.*, 2006, 2, 1.
2. Nousheen Mushtaq, Z. S. Saify, Fozia Noor, Shamoona Takween, Shamim Akhtar, Muhammad Arif and Khalid M. Khan, *Pak. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2008, 21, 36.
3. Nathalie Busso, Mahir Karababa, Massimo Nobile, Aline Rolaz, Frédéric Van Gool, Mara Galli, Oberdan Leo, Alexander So and Thibaut De Smedt, *PLoS ONE*, 2008, 3, e2267.
4. Pr.hec.gov.pk/Chapters/945-1.pdf.
5. Lalit Oberoi, Kenneth S. Alexander and Alan T. Raja, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2004, 94, 93.
6. J. Yang and J. D. Adams, *Drug Design Reviews*, 2004, 1, 43.
7. R. L. Blake, S. L. Blake, H. H. Loh and Ernest Kun, *Mol. Pharmacol.*, 1967, 3, 412.
8. Surendra Nath Pandeya, Sivakumar Smitha, Mayank Jyoti and Seshaiiah Krishnan Sridhar, *Acta Pharm.*, 2005, 55, 27.
9. G. I. Hutchison, P. A. Marshall, R. H. Prager, J. M. Tippet and A. D. Ward, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1980, 33, 2699.
10. Barbara Malawska, Katarzyna Kulig, Agnieszka Śpiewak and James P. Stables, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2004, 12, 625.
11. C. D. Boyle and A. Palani, *Current Topics in Medicinal Chemistry*, 2003, 3, 1155.

12. Shalini Mehta, Yogeeswari Perumal, Sriram Dharmarajan and Induja Sridharan, *Journal of Zhejiang University, Science (B)*, 2007, **8**, 45.
13. Santosh S. Kulkarni and Amy Hauck Newman, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2007, **17**, 2074.
14. *Alternative Medicine Review*, 2002, **7**, 525.
15. L. Pushpalatha and K. Vivekanandan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 1119.
16. L. Pushpalatha and K. Vivekanandan, *Oxid. Commun.*, 2008, **31**, 598.
17. L. Pushpalatha and K. Vivekanandan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **85**, 1027.
18. L. Pushpalatha and K. Vivekanandan, *Oxid. Commun.*, 2009, **32**, 85.
19. L. Pushpalatha and K. Vivekanandan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **86**, 475.
20. L. Pushpalatha and K. Vivekanandan, *Oxid. Commun.*, (accepted).
21. M. N. Abubacker, L. Pushpalatha and K. Vivekanandan, *International Journal of Plant Science*, 2009, **4**, 399.
22. K. Vivekanandan and K. Nambi, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1996, **35**, 1117.
23. K. Vivekanandan and K. Nambi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **76**, 198.
24. K. Vivekanandan, *Oxid. Commun.*, 2004, **27**, 195.
25. V. Ramasamy and K. Nambi, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2006, **18**, 2605; N. Mathiyalagan, *Oriental Journal of Chemistry*, 2005, **21**, 125.
26. B. Ramkumar, *Oxid. Commun.*, 2001, **24**, 554; N. Mathiyalagan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 1; N. Mathiyalagan, *Mapana Journal of Sciences*, 2005, **3**, 1.
27. R. S. Satoskar, S. D. Bhandarkar and S. S. Ainapure, "Pharmacology and Pharmacotherapeutics", Popular Prakashan, Mumbai, 2001, 184.
28. C. R. Hauser and W. B. Renfrow (Jr.), *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **59**, 121.
29. J. S. Biradar and S. Y. Manjunath, *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2004, **66**, 177.
30. P. B. Dewas, *Brit. J. Pharmacol.*, 1953, **6**, 46.
31. A. K. Misra, P. C. Dandiya and S. K. Kulkarni, *Indian J. Pharmacol.*, 1974, **5**, 449.
32. S. K. Kulkarni, "Handbook of Experimental Pharmacology", 3rd ed., Vallabhprakashan, New Delhi, 1999, 51.
33. Abdel Ghany Aly El-Helby and Mohamed Hameda Abdel Wahab, *Acta Pharm.*, 2003, **53**, 127.